

Residual Stress in High Modulus Carbon Fibers

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibers often show a variation in axial properties across the fiber diameter which leads to residual stresses. The modulus and residual strain in carbon fibers were measured by successively electrochemically milling away the fiber surface. Electrochemical etching was found to remove the carbon fiber surface very uniformly in contrast with air and wet oxidation. The precision of fiber diameter measurements was improved by using a laser diffraction technique instead of optical methods. More precise diameter measurements showed that past correlations of diameter and fiber modulus were largely measurement artifact. The moduli of most carbon fibers decreased after the outer layers of the fibers were removed. Because of experimental difficulties, the moduli and strengths of the fibers at their centers could not be determined, and moduli were estimated from microstructure. The calculated residual stresses were found to be insensitive to these moduli estimates as well as the exact form of regression equation used to describe moduli and residual strain distributions. Axial compressive residual stresses were very high for some higher modulus carbon fibers. The compressive stress makes the fibers insensitive to surface flaws when loaded in tension, but it may initiate failure by buckling when loaded in compression. Lower modulus carbon fibers were found to have much smaller residual stresses. Finally, optical activity in carbon fibers arises predominantly from preferred orientation and not residual stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Transmission electron microscopy of carbon fibers reveals an undulating ribbon structure of graphitic basal planes with higher axial alignment of the ribbons near the surface and lower alignment toward the fiber's center because of higher amplitude ribbon undulations.^{1,2,3,4,5} Optical activity, and preferred orientation determinations from electron diffraction also appear to confirm the gradient in structure in carbon fibers.^{4,6} This change in preferred orientation results in a modulus gradient with the surface material having a higher modulus and the core a lower modulus.^{4,6,7} The variation in axial preferred orientation also results in a gradient in the coefficient of thermal expansion across the fiber's diameter. Since the CTE of the graphite basal plane is lower than transverse to the plane, Work supported by NASA/AFOSR Grant NGL33-018-003 on Composite Structural Materials and the Boeing Company.

it is expected that the fiber's interior, having a higher amplitude/wavelength ribbon undulation, has a higher CTE. The varying CTE places the restrained fiber core into tension and the fiber surface into compression upon cooling from processing temperature. This surface compressive strength may account for the insensitivity of carbon fibers to surface flaws in tension,^{8,9,10,11} but it may degrade the strength in compression by initiating microbuckling.¹² During cooling from processing temperatures, radial and hoop stresses also develop within carbon fibers.^{4,13} Johnson and Watt have suggested that the optical activity that is often observed in fiber transverse section originates from residual stresses and not structure.¹⁴ These residual stresses can cause cracks to develop parallel to the fiber axis which degrade strength.¹³

Qualitative evidence for the presence of residual stress was obtained when it was observed that a fiber curled when the surface layer on just one side was ion milled away.¹² Preliminary quantitative data on residual stresses in high modulus carbon fibers (Hercules HMS) were of the order of several GPA axial compression at the surface.¹² Since then, we have developed better techniques for measuring diameter, residual strain, and also for the uniform etching of the fiber. This paper will discuss the various techniques developed to characterize microproperties, and to determine axial residual stress in carbon fibers. The effect of residual stress on optical activity will also be presented.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The determination of the residual stress requires measurement of fiber modulus and residual strain as a function of fiber diameter. Values in the past have been limited by diameter errors. Therefore, considerable effort was expended to improve the speed and precision of fiber diameter measurement. Also, much effort was used to find a technique which would uniformly remove the surface of the fiber.

1) Diameter Measurement

Optical microscopy and a laser diffraction technique were evaluated for diameter measurement of HMS carbon fibers (Table I).

TABLE I
FIBER DIAMETER MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES AND RESULTS

	Mean Diameter (μm)	Standard Deviation (μm)	Number of Observations
(A) Optical Microscopy			
(1) Edge	7.0	.45	200
(2) Vertical (Bundle)	7.81	.31	53
(3) Vertical (Single)	8.25	.25	55
(4) Oil Immersion	8.37	.11	50
(5) Image Analysis	7.74	.52	53
(B) Laser Diffraction			
(1) Photodetector	8.03	.037	18
(2) Visual	7.68	.08	30

- (1) Measured from edges of unpolished fibers laying on microscope slide.
- (2) Bundle of fibers mounted vertically in epoxy, polished diameter measured with filar eyepiece (625X).
- (3) Single fiber mounted vertically in epoxy, polished diameter measured by filar eyepiece with random position rotation of the stage and filar eyepiece viewer. (625X).
- (4) Same as (3) oil immersion (1500X).
- (5) Same as (2) but Bausch & Lomb FAS-II Image Analyser determined minimum diameter of each fiber.

A He-Ne laser beam (632.8nm wavelength) was directly aimed on a vertically mounted fiber. The diffraction pattern of the fiber was measured two ways:

- (6) Photocell masked to 1mm^2 active area and mounted on traveling microscope to detect light intensity across diffraction pattern.
- (7) Scale mounted on the image screen and intensity visually estimated.

In the optical microscopy cases, case (1) not only produced a high standard deviation, but it also resulted in a bias to smaller diameters (as might be expected). Comparison of cases (2) and (3) showed that the variance in (3) is only caused by measurement errors while in (2), the variance is due to a combination of both sample variance and measurement errors. Assuming the sample and measurement variances are independent of each other over the range studied, the sample standard deviation of 0.18 is less than the standard deviation of 0.25 due to measurement errors. (This point will be returned to in the next section.) Measurement variances can be decreased by using higher magnification to reduce vernier readout error and oil immersion to increase contrast and resolution. Comparison of (3) and (4) shows a marked decrease in standard deviation (0.11 μ) of measurement errors. Image analysis results (5) had a much higher standard deviation (0.52 μ) but mainly because of a low pixel count. Much higher magnification ("blind" magnification), to 5000X, would decrease the standard deviation to 0.2 μ . The particular image analysis technique measured the minimum diameter so as to negate the effect of non-normal mounting of the circular fibers.

The laser diffraction technique (6) and (7) has better resolution than optical microscopy for circular fiber diameter measurements, and is much faster. No mounting or polishing is required and the tedious focusing in optical microscopy is eliminated. The laser diffraction technique is also convenient for monitoring diameter continuously, as well as along the full length of a fiber.

2) Modulus Measurement

Long fibers were selected from the carbon fiber bundle, and then cut into 5cm lengths. The average fiber diameter was determined by 30 measurements along the fiber with laser diffraction. Then the fiber was thinned, its diameter re-measured, and the modulus and strength determined on a microtensile tester. In some cases, the same fiber was reloaded up to ten times, the traces compared, signal averaged, and then differentiated to evaluate any non-linearities that may exist in the stress-strain curve.

The correlation reported in the literature⁷ between fiber modulus and fiber diameter was re-examined, since diameter measurement errors produce a similar trend. (A measured fiber diameter smaller than the true fiber diameter will yield a higher modulus and vice versa.) To address this problem, Modmor I fibers of the same vintage as the literature results and recent HMS fibers were tested using laser diffraction diameter measurements. For Modmor I, the results show that the fiber is uniform along a single fiber while it varies from 7 μm to 9 μm fiber to fiber. The values of Young's modulus scatter for different fibers as shown in Figure 1. (The modulus values for HMS fibers are included for comparison.) There is no significant correlation for either fiber type between diameter and modulus in the range of diameter measured by using the improved diameter measurement technique. In fact, the earlier correlation can be shown to be artifact and can be predicted from a standard deviation of 0.11 μ in the diameter measurement. It must be stated that these results do not imply that the modulus within a carbon fiber is constant, as will be shown later.

Fig. 1: Measured Modulus Versus Diameter for Modmor I and Hercules HMS Carbon Fibers.

3) Fiber Thinning

In our earlier reported work, fibers were thinned using gaseous oxidation, wet oxidation, and ion milling. Ion milling uniformly removed the fiber surface, but was limited to small samples. Even over a wide range of conditions, wet or dry oxidation was found to non-uniformly remove material from the fibers. The problem was accentuated with higher modulus carbon fibers which had a pronounced skin/core structure. In the present studies, the surface of the carbon fiber was removed by electrochemical etching. Carbon fibers, with lengths from between 50mm to 250mm, were uniformly etched with methanol as the electrolyte, and a Pt wire, Cu wire or Nicrone wire acting as a cathode. A dc voltage ranging from 15V to 200V was applied to the system, with currents varying from .02MA to 2MA. The fiber diameter, which can be uniformly reduced by this technique from $8\mu\text{m}$ to $4.8\mu\text{m}$, was measured by laser diffraction during the experiment. SEM was used to determine the uniformity of etching both longitudinally and transversely. Uniformity along the fiber axis is shown in Figures 2(a) and (b). The surface striation on as-received HMS fibers was removed uniformly by electrochemical etching. SEM also showed that the fiber was uniformly etched across the cross-section.

Fig. 2: SEM HMS Carbon Fiber,
(a) As-Received
(b) Electrochemically Etched.

The diameter of HMS and HMU fibers were measured as a function of electrochemical etching time. Assuming the reaction rate that removes carbon is proportional to the current, a plot of $(r/r_0)^2$ versus time should be linear as shown in Figure 3(a). Although the slopes for both curves are different, the difference can be explained by the difference in initial diameters of the two fibers, $7.92\mu\text{m}$ and $9.04\mu\text{m}$ for HMS and HMU respectively. If this is corrected for by multiplying each slope by the initial radius squared, the resulting slope for each fiber is -2.17 and is equal to the rate of removal of carbon for a current of 2MA, Fig. 3(b). In the results presented later, the diameters were derived from the relation of the diameter versus time rather than individual diameter measurements. The difference was small, however.

4) Measurement of residual strain

A technique was developed to measure contraction of the fiber during electrochemical etching. A tiny glass chip was glued by black wax near the end of a single fiber with a small protruding portion of the fiber serving as an electrical contact. This fiber was mounted on a vertical translator and then put into the electrochemical cell with a mercury contact on the bottom. By moving the translator until the fiber tip contacts with the mercury, the position of the pointer is uniquely determined by the reading from translator. In these experiments, the initial position of the pointer is the most critical value for con-

Fig. 3: Etching Rate of HMS and HMU Carbon Fibers.

- (a) Normalized scale (Correlation Coefficient 0.997)
 (b) Absolute scale

traction measurements and can be precisely determined by multiple measurements. Provided the whole system is vibration free, the accuracy of the contraction measurement is .005mm.

5) Optical Measurements

The optical activity observed in carbon fibers is a function of crystalline optical anisotropy and residual stress. The question arises: What are the magnitudes of the optical activity which arises from structure and from residual stress? While the effect of structure must be an important factor in generating optical activity, particularly with longitudinal sections, the importance of residual stress is harder to estimate, as the six stress-optical coefficients for even single crystalline graphite are unknown. Even if these constants were known, it is still very complicated and questionable to adopt them for use in carbon fibers. Instead, several special experiments were performed to ascertain the effect of stress on optical activity, and to determine how much of the observed optical activity arises from residual stress. Five types of samples were metallographically prepared: 1) longitudinal sections, 2) transverse sections, 3) oblique sections, 4) loop longitudinal sections, and 5) a longitudinal section remounted for transverse observation. Optical activity on fiber areas as small as $1\mu^2$ was measured with a Leitz MPV system.

Under cross polarized light, a transverse section of an as-received HMS fiber (Figure 4) shows a string of bright spots around the circumference of the fiber with much weaker optical activity in the interior. While the circumferential optical activity is interpreted as an "onion-skin" structure of the graphite-like basal planes, the interior orientation would be much poorer and would be radial, TEM studies¹⁶ confirm the onion-skin structure, but provide no evidence for an internal radial structure. However, we have found that the interior optical activity for a fiber etched to 1/2 its original diameter is identical to the activity for the original fiber. We also found no change in optical activity for fibers that had been longitudinally polished to their mid-line and then

Fig. 4: Transverse Metallographic Section of HMS Carbon Fiber. Cross Polarized Light Magnification (after reduction): 980X. Oil Immersion

transversely viewed. Both studies show that there is no measurable effect on optical activity upon partial relief of residual stresses. Finally, a single fiber was formed into a loop with about 0.7% strain, which assuming a uniform fiber modulus gives a 2.5GPA tensile stress on the surface. (The measured modulus profiles would give even higher stresses.) A longitudinal section was metallographically prepared, and the optical activity, as measured by A_R^+ , showed only a one degree difference between the tensile and compressive edges of the fiber. This result suggests that the effect of residual stress on optical anisotropy is small compared to the structural effect. The observed optical activity was consistent with the modulus gradient determined for HMS fiber, assuming all optical activity originated from structure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Residual stress requires that both the modulus, and length change be determined as a function of etched fiber diameter.

1) Modulus Gradient

Transmission electron microscopy indicates a higher modulus outer skin on HMS and HMU fibers, Figure 5. The decrease in fiber modulus as the surface is etched away is shown in Figure 6. Because of the fragility of the etched fibers, the modulus at the center of the fiber is undetermined. However, because there is relatively little cross-section for small diameters, the value of the fiber modulus near the center of the fiber is not critical for the subsequent residual stress calculations, and in any case is not less than 60GPA or greater than 200GPA. The form of the equation for describing the modulus was selected by requiring that the modulus be continuous, smooth, emit an unique derivative at the center, and be consistent with microstructural observations.⁴ From these assumptions, a best fit cosine function, $Y(r)$, was calculated by regression analysis using all the individual points (Figure 6). The function $Y(r)$ for HMS carbon fiber is

Fig. 5: HMS Carbon Fiber.

$$Y(r) = 380 - 265 \cos \left(\frac{\pi r}{2 r_0} \right) \text{ (GPA)} \quad (1)$$

where r_0 = the radius of as-received fiber and r = the radius of etched fiber. The calculated value of average modulus at center ($r = 0$) is 115GPA, which is a little bit lower than 138GPA of a relaxed fiber⁶ (HTT 2500°C) which was not subject to tensile stress during the oxidation process. [Previous¹² fourth power function fitting sometime shows wavy near the center because of no data available in the center.] From the average modulus function $Y(r)$, the local modulus $E(r)$ at radius r can be calculated by

$$E(r) = Y(r) + \frac{r}{2} \frac{dY(r)}{dr} \quad (2)$$

or

$$E(r) = 380 - 265 \cos \left(\frac{\pi r}{2 r_0} \right) + \frac{265}{4} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right) \sin \left(\frac{\pi r}{2 r_0} \right) \quad (2a)$$

also shown in Figure 7.

The relation of average modulus to radius for etched fibers appears contradictory to the lack of correlation of average modulus to fiber diameter for as-received fibers. However, if we assume that the model of local modulus follows equation (2) and assume that the difference between fat and thin fibers within the bundle is simply due to a different size of central core, i.e., the larger the diameter the bigger the size of the core, then we can back calculate the average modulus distribution with respect to the true diameter. As shown in Figure 8, within the range of diameter distributions (25% different in diameter), the curve is relatively flat. Differences in modulus are within the measurement

Fig. 6: Measured average modulus distribution for etched HMS fiber.

Fig. 7: Local modulus distribution of HMS carbon fiber.

error.

2) Strain Gradient

Measured contractions as a function of the radius of etched fiber for Hercules HMS and HMU fibers are shown in Figure 9(a). Since HMU is the unsur-

Fig. 8: Calculated Young's modulus distribution for as-received carbon fiber. Within the range of diameter distribution (25% different in size), Young's modulus has no dependence on diameter.

face treated variant of HMS, the contraction of HMU should be similar to HMS after a thin surface layer is removed. Also because the outside has more preferred orientation with higher local modulus, HMU fiber has higher strain drop (during etching) near the surface as can be seen in Figure 9(a). The curves were overlaid in the following manner: a) The HMU and HMS curves are aligned at zero contraction at the surface ($r = r_0$); b) The HMU is shifted 500Å to the right of the HMS curve to account for the surface treatment; c) The HMU curve is shifted vertically up, about .015% strain, to obtain the best fit between the two curves; and d) The HMU curve zero contraction point is used as the reference zero point as shown in Figure 9(b).

From Figure 9(b) a best fit of cosine function can be used.

$$e(r/r_0) = -.029 - .175 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{r}{r_0}\right)$$

As can be seen in Figure 9(b) the fit close to the fiber surface is not too good. (A numerical analysis using the observed points leads to extremely high stresses at the surface.) Knowing the measured fiber contraction function, $e(r)$, the measured average modulus function, $Y(r)$, and the local modulus, $E(r)$, and assuming the actual strain gradient, $E(r)$, and its derivative is continuous, an equation can be formed by balancing the forces within a fiber of radius r and solving for $E(r)$, Figure 10.

$$E(r) = -e(r) - \frac{de(r)}{dr} \frac{\int_0^r rE(r)dr}{rE(r)} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 9: Measured contraction versus radius change by electrochemical etching for HMU and HMS fibers (a) absolute scale (b) shift the data to make best fitting.

Fig. 10: Residual stress and residual strain of HMS carbon fiber.

3) Residual Stress

Once the local modulus and local strain have been established, the residual stress within carbon fibers is the product of modulus and strain at each location within the fibers, Figure 10. The fiber is observed to have a tensile axial residual stress in the center of the fiber with a compressive axial stress at the surface. The tensile residual stress in the middle of the fiber is not very sensitive to the form of the functions used for the modulus and strain gradients, provided the function emits a unique derivative at the center of the fiber. However, the calculated compressive stress at the surface is dependent upon the type of curves used. The calculated residual stress near the surface is about .35GPA, but rapidly increases as the surface is approached.

4) Consequences on Fiber Properties

While high surface compression minimizes the effect of surface flaws,¹⁰ the high axial tensile stress in the interior may decrease strength by causing fracture to initiate at flaws in the interior rather than at the surface. Similarly, the high axial compressive stressed outer layers of a fiber may initiate buckling when the fiber is compressively loaded. Modifications of the residual stress pattern might allow increased tensile and/or compressive strengths to be obtained in high modulus carbon fibers. A modulus gradient also exists within carbon fibers. The modulus of the surface layers is about twice the average fiber modulus while the interior modulus is only about one-half the average. This modulus gradient suggests that higher modulus carbon fibers could be produced if the modulus at the interior of these fibers could be increased.

CONCLUSIONS

The gradient in microstructure of HMS carbon fibers introduces residual stresses into the fibers upon cool-down from processing temperatures. The surface layer of the fiber is in axial compression and the interior is in axial tension. The residual stresses appear to be large enough to affect fiber strength.

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